

[2nd Nov 1972]

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Dear David Insall,

Thank you very much for ^{your} two ~~not~~ helpful and straightforward letters. Your latest letter arrived just in time for me to scrap the reply I had written!

You do seem to be ^{having} ~~being~~ a most eventful time on the archaeological front. Let's hope that with good management this will be the start of the archaeological "discovery" of Oman. The country has such potential in ^{which} all periods ~~is~~ cries out for investigation.

I must first tell you of ^{events} ~~XXXXXXXXXX~~ from my end. Since hearing from you I have had first a tentative and just now a ^{formal} invitation from one of the expeditions you mention (the American one sponsored by Harvard University) ^{to} to join them as their archaeologist concerned with the post Hellenistic periods. I welcomed the opportunity to join a financially stable project provided this will not reduce my own ^{chances of obtaining permission} opportunities of ^{to examine} examining the more recent sites in Oman. (^{the other 2, I suppose are for Oman + called for to British Museum} ~~the other 2, I suppose are for Oman + called for to British Museum~~ ^{both of which returned Bahrain as their objective!})

It does seem very well advised to leave consideration of these expeditions for the advice of Karin Frifeld ^{me} as you mention one wishes to avoid ill feelings or overlap. I am, though, sad to learn that the British Expedition to Bahrein (from the British Museum) plans to include ^{it} Oman in its scope. For whatever groups do work in Oman, ~~it~~ can hardly be in ^{the Sultanate's best interest} ~~the best interests~~ if it is to be dominated by a British or Danish mission whose primary interests lie in Arabia outside Oman.

~~(The other expedition in Bahrein that for Durham University is to be the lead to work in Bahrein year)~~

A country with the size and wealth of the Sultanate deserves to be ^{run} better
^{to be a} than ~~inside~~ show to projects whose major effort lies outside.

Thank you for your information. I shall write to Kiren, and I appreciate
very greatly your ~~advice~~ ^{advice} in Muscat. Perhaps since my interests are
rather later than those of

My personal interests lie principally in the more recent periods and
for that reason I hope that I would not be treading on anyone else's toes.
^{consensual} The importance of Oman in the Sassanian and Islamic periods ^{has been} ~~has been~~ ^{very} ~~seriously~~
^{over some few examples.} neglected. ~~For example one rather reliable 10th century source~~
^{into 10c called A.D. called} (The Hadid ~~XX~~ al Alam) ^{wrote} of Suhar "The entrepot of the whole world;
with the richest ^{markets} in the world. All the products of the East, the
West, the South and the North are carried to that town and transported to
different places" and this ^{is} ~~is~~ one reference among many. ^{There is abundant}
a great deal of ^{very much} ~~archaeological material~~ ^{evidence} for this to be found.

Thank you ^{very much} for your advice. I shall certainly write to Karen, and I do
greatly appreciate your good offices in ^{Muscat} ~~Muscat~~. If I could come at
^{MUSCAT} government expense that would be ideal, failing that I can obtain funds for
my return travel from my college. I have already spent 3 years on the
Gulf (I am currently busy publishing it) and if in the future an opportunity
does come up for an archaeological job in Oman I do at least realize what
sort of climate I would be letting myself in for! In any case I hope
very much that I ~~shall be able to visit Oman this winter.~~ ^{conditions at you}
^{and} ~~will enable me to visit Oman this winter.~~ ^{I very} ~~much~~
much look forward to seeing the ~~country~~ ^{country} & to ~~reaching~~ ^{reaching} you

Yours really
A.D. Wilson

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